

Workshop 1

Cineflux agent: vision

We seek to create a minimum viable product (MVP) that leverages film-review data and digital FG data to provide deep conversational and visual explanations of how specific audiences from country X perceive the productions coming from another country Y , where X and Y can be **general (Danish people on Irish films), or **specified over a hierarchy of relevant audience variables** (Portuguese women perceptions of Spanish comedy).**

Broad example: Portuguese films

General audiences

Morality and ethical complexity: redemption, social justice, personal responsibility.

National and cultural identity: post dictatorship society, cultural objects and symbols, music.

Visuals: stunning landscapes, intimate and surreal urban scenes.

Narrative style and plot: slow burn, melancholic, contemplative, layered.

Emotion: melancholy, introspection, loneliness.

General Spanish audience

Nice visuals but far too slow, depressing, fell-asleep, long-winded, no sense of humour.

Challenge

We seek to define an audience model specific to film based on a hierarchy of relevant and informative variables that can be computed from review and conversation (FG) data. We are leveraging large language models, which will probably be supported by additional systems (e.g., semantic networks from Wikipedia). This hierarchy-based model of film audiences does not exist and would be a key contribution.

With this model, we will build a (demo, MVP) conversational + visual explanatory system for funders and public institutions (to inform strategic decisions that increase the competitiveness of European films).

Data

Film reviews are rich cultural texts encapsulating opinions and social narratives about art, e.g. films.

Focus groups can capture similar data, but in a very nuanced manner, e.g. specific films x demographics.

Streamlined surveys before film exposure, as well as before and after FGs can target specific variables.

Model

We are analysing review data using various LLMs and approaches to see what can be computed, while in parallel, we are looking at various theoretical models that incorporate dimensions such as sentiment and stance, ethics and morality, opinion dynamics, and others.

Progress in the model component is essential for designing the questionnaires that will be used in the context of the FG activities.

If you're drawn to the ways humans and technology co-create meaning in our world, you may find my Substack worth reading. I write to explore, but also to engage—speaking to this community matters to me because the conversations it sparks shape the very questions I'm asking.

themeaningmachine.substack.com

Approach

Deep **explanations** of past trends from reliable data at scale.

Innovation (and challenge)

What are the informative dimensions?
Can we measure them computationally and at scale?

Cast & crew · User reviews · Trivia | IMDbPro | All topics | Share

The Girl with the Needle

Original title: Pigen med nålen
2024 · 15 · 2h 3m

IMDb RATING **7.5**/10
11K
YOUR RATING **Rate**
POPULARITY **114** ▲8

Play trailer 1:31 | I have a new life. 31 likes 13 hearts

1 VIDEO

99+ PHOTOS

Drama History

Copenhagen 1919: A young worker finds herself unemployed and pregnant. She meets Dagmar, who runs an underground adoption agency. A strong connection grows but her world shatters when she stumbles on the shocking truth behind her work.

Director [Magnus von Horn](#)

Writers [Magnus von Horn](#) · [Line Langebek Knudsen](#)

Stars [Vic Carmen Sonne](#) · [Trine Dyrholm](#) · [Besir Zeciri](#)

IMDbPro See production info at IMDbPro

+ Add to Watchlist
Added by 31.2K users

40 User reviews 91 Critic reviews

82 Metascore

Details

Edit

Release date [January 17, 2025 \(Poland\)](#)

Countries of origin [Denmark](#) · [Poland](#) · [Sweden](#) · [France](#) · [Belgium](#)

Language [Danish](#)

Also known as [Cô Gái và Cây Kim](#)

Filming locations [Kłodzko, Dolnoslaskie, Poland](#)

Production companies [Nordisk Film Production](#) · [Creative Alliance](#) · [Lava Films](#)

See more company credits at IMDbPro

Box office

Edit

Gross US & Canada

\$111,343

Opening weekend US & Canada

\$15,284 · Dec 8, 2024

Gross worldwide

\$485,908

IMDbPro See detailed box office info on IMDbPro

Cast & crew · User reviews · Trivia · FAQ
IMDbPro
All topics

Kneecap

2024 · 18 · 1h 45m

IMDb RATING

★ 7.6/10
16K

YOUR RATING

☆ Rate

POPULARITY

🔥 626 ▾ 429

Play trailer 2:23

👍 101 🌟 29

1 VIDEO

89 PHOTOS

Dark Comedy
Docudrama
Comedy
Drama
Music

When fate brings Belfast teacher JJ into the orbit of self-confessed "low life scum" Naoise and Liam Óg, the needle drops on a hip hop act like no other. Rapping in their native Irish, they lead a movement to save their mother tongue.

Director [Rich Peppiatt](#)

Writers [Rich Peppiatt](#) · [Móglai Bap](#) · [Mo Chara](#) >

Stars [Móglai Bap](#) · [Mo Chara](#) · [DJ Próvai](#) >

+ Add to Watchlist
Added by 37.3K users

81 User reviews · 112 Critic reviews

76 Metascore

+ Add to Watchlist
Added by 37.3K users

IMDbPro See production info at IMDbPro

Details

Edit

Release date [August 23, 2024 \(United Kingdom\)](#) >

Countries of origin [Ireland](#) · [United Kingdom](#)

Official sites [Official Irish website](#) > · [Official Site](#) >

Languages [English](#) · [Irish Gaelic](#)

Also known as [嘻蓋骨男孩](#) >

Filming locations [Belfast, Northern Ireland, UK](#) >

Production companies [British Film Institute \(BFI\)](#) · [Coimisiún na Meán](#) · [Curzon Film Distributors](#) >

See more company credits at IMDbPro >

Box office

Edit

Gross US & Canada

\$1,145,143

Opening weekend US & Canada

\$470,977 · Aug 4, 2024

Gross worldwide

\$4,578,889

IMDbPro [See detailed box office info on IMDbPro](#) >

Cast & crew · User reviews · IMDbPro · All topics

On Falling

2024 · 15 · 1h 44m

Drama

The story focuses on Aurora, a Portuguese worker in a Scottish warehouse, navigating loneliness and alienation in an algorithm-driven gig economy as she seeks meaning and connection amidst solitude and workplace confines.

Director [Laura Carreira](#)

Writer [Laura Carreira](#)

Stars [Joana Santos](#) · [Inês Vaz](#) · [Piotr Sikora](#)

IMDbPro See production info at IMDbPro

IMDb RATING ★ 7.4/10 (251)

YOUR RATING ☆ [Rate](#)

Add to Watchlist
Added by 1.2K users

3 User reviews · 16 Critic reviews

Details

Edit

Release date [October 17, 2024 \(United Kingdom\)](#)

Countries of origin [United Kingdom](#) · [Portugal](#)

Languages [English](#) · [Portuguese](#)

Also known as Σε πτώση

Filming locations [Edinburgh, Scotland, UK](#)

Production companies [BBC Film](#) · [BRO Cinema](#) · [Loudness Films](#)

See more company credits at IMDbPro

Tech specs

Edit

Runtime 1 hour 44 minutes

Color [Color](#)

Awards 4 wins & 6 nominations total

Photos

6

+ Add photo

More to explore

Cast & crew · User reviews · Trivia · IMDbPro · All topics

Jon Vardar protiv Galaksijata

2024 · 1h 26m

Animation · Comedy · Sci-Fi

One completely unexceptional man. One emotionally unstable robot with a huge spaceship - and many, many, many aliens. On a mission to save (or destroy) the Galaxy.

Director [Goce Cvetanovski](#)

Writer [Goce Cvetanovski](#)

Stars
[Zarko Dimoski](#) · [Damjan Cvetanovski](#) · [Emilija Micevska](#)

IMDbPro [See production info at IMDbPro](#)

IMDb RATING **9.0**/10
59

YOUR RATING [★ Rate](#)

COMING SOON
Releases March 27, 2025

[+ Add to Watchlist](#)

5 User reviews

Details

Edit

- Release date** [March 27, 2025 \(Hungary\)](#)
- Countries of origin** [North Macedonia](#) · [Croatia](#) · [Hungary](#) · [Bulgaria](#)
- Official site** [Official site](#)
- Language** [Macedonian](#)
- Also known as** [John Vardar vs. a galaxis](#)
- Production companies** [Lynx Animation Studios](#) · [3D2D Animatori](#) · [Invictus](#)
- See more company credits at IMDbPro**

Box office

Edit

Budget
 €1,132,978 (estimated)
 IMDbPro [See detailed box office info on IMDbPro](#)

Awards 3 nominations total

More to explore

Photos 8

[+ Add photo](#)

Getting a baseline model requires reliable data

Reviews collected from Rotten Tomatoes and Letterboxd: COUNTS

movie	total_reviews	RT_critic_reviews	RT_audience_reviews	letterboxd_reviews
GIRL	3152	74	7	3071
KNEE	3329	133	124	3072
FALL	277	6	0	271
JOHN	9	0	0	9

Data collection happened in January. We will run a collection update.

Reviews collected from Rotten Tomatoes and Letterboxd: LENGTH

movie	Review Length (words)
GIRL	8-55 (median 20)
KNEE	5-26 (median 12)
FALL	8-60 (median 25)
JOHN	15-24 (median 17)

Some facts

1. Audience reviews -> Letterboxd
2. Critic reviews -> Rotten Tomatoes
3. Letterboxd reviews have social endorsement as likes.
4. Letterboxd-registered users can comment on reviews.

What have we been doing?

1. Analysing different language models with multilingual capabilities.
2. The goal: exploring model suitability for 7.3 goals.
3. We are looking at contextual and sentence-level models (BERT-based).
4. But also at models with large inputs and contexts like Llama and chatGPT.
5. We are optimising for model suitability + open access + lightweight.
6. We have optimised the Cineflux platform so that it can run large numbers of debates simultaneously

What is next?

1. Explore Letterboxd audience reviews from the lens of the works presented in the workshop. End of March
2. Produce outputs that inform the dimensions of the audience model. Mid April
3. Use the chosen dimensions to produce survey questions and moderation script for CineFlux FGs. End of April

Goal: to have everything ready for Cineflux activities early May.

What are we worried about?

We've discussed the focus on biases—how audiences from country Y perceive productions from country X. However, our MVP is built around four films where the narrative itself can challenge or reshape audience dimensions. For instance, *On Falling* will likely “push” moral perceptions in ways that may diverge from general biases about films from Portugal.

This calls for a more nuanced discussion as we refine our approach.

Workshop 2

WP 7.3 Second technical workshop 24 March 2025

From the roadmap: explore Letterboxd audience reviews from the lens of the works presented in the first workshop.

Deadline: end of March 2025

Today we have exploratory results for Letterboxd audience reviews of ‘Girl with the needle’ and ‘Kneecap’. This analysis is exploratory: we are identifying initial dimensions to formalize our final model within schedule.

Exploratory data analysis method in a nutshell

1. Focus on **'Girl with the needle'** and **'Kneecap'**
2. Performed **topic modelling** to cluster reviews
3. **Mixed-method interpretation of review clusters** on two levels:
 - a. LLM supported **coherence analysis and summarization**
 - b. Extraction of **most frequently used verbs and adjectives**
4. **Sampled reviews from each cluster** to generate:
 - a. Qualitative **estimates of morality + values scores**
 - b. Qualitative **estimates of bias + preconception scores**

1. Hierarchical Stochastic Block Topic Modelling

What it does

- Automatically finds themes (topics) and sub-themes in large collections of text.
- Organizes words and documents into clusters based on how frequently they appear together.
- Builds a hierarchy of topics and subtopics, showing how themes connect or nest within each other.
- Provides an interpretable “map” of the main ideas hidden in the corpus.

Method at a glance

- Input: A big set of texts (user reviews).
- Process: The model detects recurring patterns of word use and groups them.
- Output: A layered structure of topics, from broad categories down to finer details.

Why do we use it?

To find hidden topical structure in the review data, if the structure exists

Girl with the needle. 1402 reviews in English. HSBM Topic model

What themes resonate most with audiences?

Interpretation part II: top verbs and adjectives

1. We took a sample of 100 reviews for each topic-cluster (or all reviews if less than 100)
2. Used Python's spaCy library for English to:
 1. Tokenize the text.
 2. Identify part-of-speech tags.
 3. Filter for VERB (ADJ) tokens.
 4. Counted frequency of lemmas (the "base forms" of each verb).
3. Selected the top verbs by raw count (excluding auxiliary/helping verbs like "be," "have," "do," etc., which dominate in everyday English but don't carry as much semantic weight).

Note: only showing the results for the largest clusters.

Critical reflections and cultural observations

Top verbs

- **Think** → express opinions
- **See** → more people to see and discuss
- **Feel** → sick, oddly paced
- **Watch** → best, if you can
- **Happen** → plot development
- **Go** → to describe deeper
- **Love** → cinematography, used in irony

Top adjectives

- *Dark* → film's atmosphere
- *Bleak* → most used mood descriptor
- *Haunting* → psychological effects
- *Disturbing* → effect on viewer
- *Beautiful* → cinematography, photography
- *Miserable* → reflects extreme negative sentiment of the film
- *Incredible* → making of the film

“A powerful exploration of how a single needle can carry the weight of an entire culture’s anxieties, showcasing **the quiet devastation beneath societal norms and the relentless pressure of conformity**. It forces us to rethink **not just personal morality, but collective responsibility**.”

Emotional shock and trauma from the film

Top verbs

- **Watch** → Dominant (never again)
- **Feel** → numb, horrified
- **Love** → the filmmaking, contrasting
- **Traumatize** → deeply, to the core
- **Recommend** → “could never”
- **Think** → state opinions
- **Warn** → be warned if you choose to see

Top adjectives

- *Bleak* → most used mood descriptor
- *Disturbing* → effect on viewer
- *Dark* → film’s atmosphere
- *Horrifying* → emphasis on terror
- *Traumatic* → emotional impact
- *Depressing* → heavy, sad

“This was absolutely shattering—**emotionally raw, deeply traumatising, and impossible to shake off.** The intensity with which the film portrays **personal anguish and violation** left me stunned, unable to stop thinking about it days after watching.”

Narrative existential analysis of postwar horrors

Top verbs

- **Tell** → narrative of the story
- **Use** → of resources to tell the story
- **Depict** → narrative
- **Unfold** → narrative
- **Survive** → key focus, people post war
- **Make** → Director intent and choices
- **Grapple** → moral, philosophical wrestling with horror.

Top adjectives

- *Bleak* → most used mood descriptor
- *Dark* → film's atmosphere
- *Haunting* → effect on viewer
- *Disturbing* → effect on viewer
- *Brutal* → emphasis on terror
- *Horrific* → emotional impact
- *Beautiful* → “shot in B&W”

“The film captures an **existential dread** rooted deeply in **postwar anxiety** —haunted by the past yet fearful of the future. It feels like a grim meditation on the **meaninglessness of survival**, where horror isn't in monsters but in confronting humanity's **loss of purpose** in the wake of war.”

How we used LLMs to estimate morality and bias scores

- (1) **Heuristic reading:** agent read through each review sample from topic cluster, looking for moral or ethical judgments (e.g. “evil,” “disturbing,” “wrong”) and cultural or national bias (like “Brits out”).
- (2) **Key cues:** agent used frequency and sentiment to find condemned or approved actions, plus any overt hostility or bias toward specific groups.
- (3) **0–1 Scale:** Gave an approximate intensity rating, from very few references (near 0) to extremely frequent and/or high sentiment arousal (close to 1).
- (4) **Context matters:** If a statement seemed ironic or joking, agent weighed it differently than if it came off as serious or hostile.
- (5) **Comparisons across topic clusters:** agent checked overall patterns and how dominant the moral or biased content was in each batch of reviews to finalize the score.

Girl with the needle. Morality and bias estimated scores

TC	Topic cluster description	Morality	Bias
1	Expansive Critical Reflections and Cultural Observations	0.7	0.4
2	Overwhelming Shock and Trauma from the Film	0.6	0.3
3	Philosophical Refrain: “The World Is a Horrible Place...”	0.7	0.4
4	Real-Life Inspiration, Bodily Autonomy, and Post-WWI Hardship	0.8	0.4
5	Oscar Race Closure: A Brutal Yet Spellbinding Final Watch	0.8	0.3
6	Reality Revealed: The Shock of “Inspired by True Events.”	0.7	0.4
7	In-Depth Cinematic and Existential Analysis of Postwar Horror	0.8	0.4
8	A Bleak Moral Landscape: Abortion Politics and Post-War Survival	0.8	0.3
9	Oscars & Aesthetic Brutality: A Meta-Critical Deep Dive	0.8	0.3
10	Raw Fury: An Expletive-Laden, Visceral Reaction to “The Girl with the Needle”	0.3	0.4

Kneecap. 2354 reviews in English. HSBM Topic model

What themes resonate most with audiences?

Kneecap. 2354 reviews in English. HSBM Topic model

What themes resonate most with audiences?

“I fucking hate Margaret Thatcher too lads. They really snubbed so many good movies at the Oscars this year just to give Emilia Perez nominations. Solid movie, fun Irish history, fuck the system type of movie, rap influence in other countries—would watch again. This will never not slap. Why was this actually good? Proud to be Irish, it was everything I wanted.”

“never felt more patriotic about a place I’m not from, that shot of Fassbender in the middle of the jumping crowd is so sick, it was funny and now I wanna go learn Gaeilge, which I guess is the point. Also, the music was pretty good. A Luis Guzmán recommendation banger—they were playing themselves. Honestly thought they were all actors making a fictional story till the very end.”

“Fuck the Brits, fuck colonisation, burn them all. Fucking love Irish people even though they probably hate me. Vibing to music even though I don’t understand the lyrics. No problem—years of listening to anime soundtracks have prepared me for this.”

“Kneecap is a special kind of music biopic. One thing that sets it apart is that the band members of the real-life band Kneecap play themselves, and they do an incredible job. With the disarming charisma of natural performers, they carry the film with ease.”

User reactions to Kneecap

Gaelic revival and neon tracksuits:
Kneecap’s infectious Irish spirit.

Drugs, beats, and gaelic rebellion:
an Irish Hip-Hop journey

A film about the Gaelic-rap group
Kneecap

Kneecap. Morality and bias estimated scores

TC	Topic cluster description	Morality	Bias
1	A film about the Gaelic-rap group Kneecap	0.5	0.8
2	Drugs, beats, and gaelic rebellion: an Irish Hip-Hop journey	0.6	0.7
3	User reactions to Kneecap	0.4	0.8
4	Gaelic revival and neon tracksuits: Kneecap's infectious Irish spirit.	0.5	0.8

Preliminary comparison

Morality and Values

<i>Girl with the needle</i>	<i>Kneecap</i>
<p>High moral intensity around infanticide, cruelty, patriarchy, historical oppression. Many reviews used words like horrifying, disturbing, morally wrong, bleak.</p>	<p>Morality references were more comedic or fleeting. People joked about “doing drugs” or “rebellious,” but it wasn’t a deep moral condemnation or defense.</p>
<p>The aggregated “morality and values” measure was often high (~0.7–0.8 on a 0-1 scale) because reviewers engaged with right vs. wrong or moral condemnation.</p>	<p>So, “morality” was moderate, around 0.4. People had personal stances on right to cultural identity or independence, but the tone was mostly irreverent or comedic.</p>

Preliminary comparison

Bias and preconceptions

<i>Girl with the needle</i>	<i>Kneecap</i>
Some references to “Scandinavians” or “Danes,” but the text included little explicit preconceptions, hostility or nationalistic fervor.	Repeated anti-British slogans, “Brits out,” references to Irish vs. English tension, explicit pro-Irish nationalism. Users strongly champion Gaelic identity.
The bias was low-moderate, around ~0.3–0.4. The negativity was more about the time period or tragedies, not a direct condemnation of a current culture.	This was consistently described as high (~0.7–0.8). The cultural tension is a driving theme, and many reviews contained direct cultural biases.

Why do these dimensions seem to matter?

- **Narrative fit:** public film funders may want to know if a project will spark moral debate, or if it risks alienating certain cultural groups and compare that with similar past trends.
- **Potential for social impact:** a film with strong moral/ethical commentary can provoke discussion or policy reflection. Alternatively, a film with strong cultural biases might mobilize niche audiences or alienate broader ones.
- **Forecasting controversy vs. engagement:** a film that triggers intense moral reactions or cultural bias might
 - (a) Go “viral” due to controversy
 - (b) Face pushback that hinders distribution.

Either way, it's relevant to funders evaluating impact potential.

Beyond these two dimensions: triangulation with other variables

- **Revenue:** a purely moral or culturally charged film might have “viral” potential but limited mainstream success. Combine the moral/cultural metrics with box-office or streaming data from similar projects.
- **Media coverage:** films that spark moral outrage or cultural debate often get extra press—this coverage can amplify success or bury a film in controversy.
- **Prizes and recognition:** industry awards or festival buzz can offset negative audience reactions (or might never come if the film is too controversial).
- **Demographic fit:** who do you expect to watch the film? A younger, more politically active audience might respond differently to moral/cultural cues than older, conservative demographics.

Preliminary critical reflection (based on exploratory insights)

“The Girl with the Needle” is morally charged, bleak, and focuses on historical trauma. That might yield strong moral talk but less comedic or intangible bias. It might attract arthouse fans who reflect on moral dilemmas.

“Kneecap” triggers identity-based fervor, comedic anti-British stances, and is presumably more fun, rebellious. It can produce intense (but different) engagement from watchers proud of Irish culture or those who love “edgy” humour.

The two films happened to be prototypes of these dimensions, will this generalise?

Going deeper into the dimensions (ongoing work, this is not final)

Next steps

1. Focus on the **Morality** and **Bias** dimensions, but with an orthogonal “**Universal** vs. **Local**” dimension
2. These **dimensions will be further unpacked into a hierarchy** of variables
3. We need to **formalize method to quantify these dimensions** (we used exploratory estimates)
4. Design the CineFlux surveys and moderator scripts
5. We still think we should have **pre-viewing, pre-chat** and **post-chat** surveys
6. **Surveys must be minimal and strategically designed**, rather than cognitively taxing
7. Note. **CineFlux Chat will be autonomous**, we will not need people to moderate the chat sessions.
8. More **logistic details about CineFlux Chat will follow via shared document next week.**

How is it going? 14 April.

1. Explore Letterboxd audience reviews from the lens of the works presented in the workshop.

End of March

2. Produce outputs that inform the dimensions of the audience model.

Mid April

3. Use the chosen dimensions to produce survey questions and moderation script for CineFlux FGs.

End of April

- 1. Need to **expand film pool** for data driven validation.
- 2. **Significant progress on theoretically grounded computational model.**
- 3. Some **delay is anticipated with some impact on subtask 3.**
- 4. **Push CineFlux data collection to June.**

Goal: to have everything ready for Cineflux activities early May.

Theoretical Model for Film Audience Characterisation

Goal

Develop a hierarchical multidimensional model to systematically analyse and characterise film audience reactions in reviews.

Dimensions and variables (work in progress)

1. **Morality:** Moral alignment, ethical reasoning, moral emotions
2. **Bias:** Cultural/National biases, confirmation biases, narrative biases
3. **Cultural Identity:** Individualism vs. Collectivism, self-construal, ethnic identity
4. **Hedonic Motivations:** Enjoyment, escapism, thrill-seeking, mood regulation
5. **Eudaimonic Motivations:** Meaningfulness, reflection, mixed emotions, self-development, empathy and connection

Justification

Dimensions and variables explicitly derived from leading literature:

Oliver & Raney (2011), Tamborini et al. (2010), Odag et al. (2018), Wirth et al. (2012), Oliver & Bartsch (2010, 2011)

Theoretical Model for Film Audience Characterisation

Challenge

Need scientific replicability & objective measurements (no subjective scoring by LLM).

Solution

Fine-grained binary feature vectors:

Each dimension/variable broken down into binary indicators.

e.g., Cultural Bias →

1. “Country X negatively portrayed (0/1)”
2. “Country Y positively portrayed (0/1)”
3. Explicit semantic markers and dictionaries: **Carefully constructed, literature-based term dictionaries ensure objective presence/absence detection.**

LLM agents are used to check for the presence or absence of each micro-feature for each variable in each dimension.

Example (Cultural Bias variable)

<i>Feature</i>	<i>Binary</i>
<i>Explicit negative portrayal (Country X)</i>	<i>0/1</i>
<i>Historical conflict explicitly cited</i>	<i>0/1</i>
<i>Stereotypes explicitly mentioned</i>	<i>0/1</i>

System architecture

Each dimension-variable pairing is analysed by a specialised LLM agent.

Agent task (example):

1. Receives film review text
2. Uses crafted dictionaries + few shot prompting and explicit instructions to detect features
3. Returns objective, replicable binary feature vector for assigned variable

Final combined output: Large, structured, replicable feature vector characterising each film review across all dimensions and variables.

Why this method?

1. Fully reproducible and comparable across reviews, films, and contexts.
2. Scientific rigour and interpretability
3. Scalable, applicable across contexts (e.g., any pair of cultural identities)
4. Low dimensional binary vectors are amenable to solid computational analysis

Challenges

1. There is significant manual crafting of features vectors, dictionaries, etc.
2. We need to go beyond GWTN and KNEECAP to prioritise dimensions + vars because we may be unable to use a detailed model due to time constraints.

May 12 2025 UPDATE

Summary of 12 May 2025 updates on 7.3

1. **Previous work: two-dimensional audience model, girl-with-the-needle and kneecap.**
2. **Constraints and opportunities moving forward:**
 - (a) A novel five-dimensional audience model.
 - (b) Requirement for more review data to saturate + validate the new model.
 - (c) Impact (delay) on planned Cineflux conversation activities, *starting no sooner than mid-June.*
 - (d) Impact on moving forward faster with the CineFlux *Dashboard mock-up by the end of July.*
3. **Next steps:**
 - (e) Saturate the new model with collected review data DK + PT since 2020 (next two weeks).
 - (f) Validate and fine-tune the model (at this point, it is only based on theory).
 - (g) Use results to design the appropriate user surveys and chat mod scripts (for ▲)
 - (h) Use results to work on the dashboard mockup.
4. **Use cases: We have worked on precisely how the CineFlux dashboard can support funders.**

WP 7.3 plan and updates

<i>Task</i>	<i>Planned</i>	<i>Status</i>	<i>Adjust</i>
Analyse reviews for selected films.	<i>End of March</i>	<i>DONE, outcome: we need more data, which has now been collected.</i>	
Produce outputs that inform the dimensions of the audience model.	<i>Mid April</i>	<i>Partially done. We have a model, need to validate + refine it on more review data.</i>	<i>Needs about two extra weeks</i>
<i>Cineflux moderation scripts + surveys</i>	<i>End of April (delayed)</i>	<i>Needs to be tied to baseline validation, some of it to be done in parallel.</i>	<i>End of May</i>
<i>CineFlux activities</i>	<i>May (delayed)</i>	<i>Needs triangulation mod scripts and surveys.</i>	<i>Start in mid June.</i>
<i>Using the new data we can move forward with the operationalisation of the audience model</i>	<i>Dashboard mock-up end of July</i>	<i>This will help us compensate for the delays and put us back on track.</i>	
<i>Model triangulation with collected CineFlux data</i>	<i>TBD</i>	<i>We bring CineFlux data into an already mocked-up dashboard and move to MVP.</i>	

Initial findings

1. **Initial Insights:** Letterboxd reviews of *Girl with the Needle* and *Kneecap* were found to be paradigmatic of the two foundational dimensions of our comparative audience model: *Morality* and *Bias*. This led us to question the proper method for informing our generic audience model baseline.
2. **Data enhancement:**
 1. Expanded dataset: Collected 200k+ reviews for the 72 most popular films primarily produced by either PT or DK each year since 2020 (total 720).
 2. Collected a cultural multidimensional reference dataset for 67 countries. Values, Morality and Culture.
 3. Developed a nuanced baseline analysis to move beyond single data points.
3. **Rationale:**
 1. Relying on only two films is insufficient to develop a robust and representative baseline for PT and DK audiences.
 2. Broader sampling is essential to capture audience diversity and nuanced opinions and mitigate biases tied to single-film anomalies.
 3. This will also help validate our extended audience model before we move to the CineFlux DFGs.
4. **We produced an in-depth research report on EU film funding and intercultural resonance (to be shared)**

Extended audience model

1. Model extension

1. Expanded our audience comparison model from two to five dimensions based on deep theoretical exploration.
2. We will fine-tune the model based on its application to the collected DK and PT data.

2. Innovative methodology

1. Implementing a nuanced LLM-based scoring system to quantify these dimensions reliably.
2. Systematically informing each dimension with carefully designed micro-variables via yes/no prompts to the LLM.
3. Aggregating these responses algorithmically into a five-level scale compatible with state-of-the-art (SOTA) methods.

3. **Impact and sustainability:** our model is designed to inform policy-makers with sufficient nuance and adaptability for diverse decision-making scenarios (policy vectors defined as parameters).

Theoretical Model for Film Audience Characterisation

1. Five dimensions.
2. Three hierarchical levels.
3. Bottom level is micro features.
4. Features are saturated via Y/N questions to LLM.
5. We process saturation to get reliable quantification.

How will Cineflux support funders?

Cultural subgroups and market balance

Clearly **define cultural subgroup clusters** (e.g., linguistic, regional, identity-based) **to ensure equitable representation**, specifically bridging small-market producers with large and other small-market audiences.

Cultural subgroups and market balance

Cultural subgroups and market balance

Intercultural resonance

Prioritise parameters that identify and quantify intercultural appeal.
Align this with EU objectives to enhance the cross-border circulation of films and cultural exchange.

ation

Audience-centric metrics

Decision-making

Intercultural resonance

policy integration

Audience-centric metrics

Incorporate metrics such as audience engagement, emotional response, and cultural relatability to inform which films resonate broadly, directly supporting EU's emphasis on cross-cultural impact.

Data-driven decision-making

54

Interce

EU policy integration

Audience-cent

Ensure that parametrisation explicitly incorporates current EU film funding goals outlined in Creative Europe MEDIA guidelines, including diversity, transnational distribution, and support for low audiovisual capacity countries.

Leverage our model's analytics to support decision-making with solid explanatory insights based on past trends in cross-cultural audience reception, enhancing funding decisions based on measurable potential rather than purely artistic intuition or historical precedent.

Data-driven decision-making

Cultural subgroups are

EU policy integration

Hypothetical example

1. Define three subgroups (they could be anything).
2. Prioritise funding films based on, e.g. the network above (4).
3. Match candidate projects against our model.
4. Ensure adherence to EU policies.
5. Qualify the statistical significance of the model output.

Country level data

1. Explore Letterboxd audience reviews from the lens of the works presented in the workshop.

End of March

2. Produce outputs that inform the dimensions of the audience model.

Mid April

Goal: to have everything ready for Cineflux activities early May.

3. Use the chosen dimensions to produce survey questions and moderation script for CineFlux FGs.

End of April

Update.

1. **The goal was overoptimistic;** this kind of comparative audience model is novel, complex, and needs to be theoretically grounded. We have been studying a body of relevant previous research.
2. **We just completed the first version of the stable model.**
3. **Subtask 3 above will start this week** (the second week of May), and we expect it to be completed by 20 May.
4. **We also need to recruit test subjects in PT to test the new CineFlux chat platform around May 20.**
5. **We need to rethink when to run the chats.** The most optimistic scenario is mid-June.

Research workshop: May 26

Why a comparative MVP?

Goal: let any funder/stakeholder position any audience group (country, region, niche cohort) on the space of a film with the same 5-dimensional vector from large volumes of data (in minutes, not months.)

Pay-off: early green-red-lighting, cross-border marketing pivots, evidence for public-funding bodies.

Theoretical Model for Film x Audience Characterisation

1. Five dimensions.
2. Three hierarchical levels.
3. Bottom level is micro features.
4. Features are saturated via Y/N questions to LLM.
5. We process saturation to get reliable quantification.

- ① CULTURAL CONTEXT (macro fit between film and group culture)
 - ② Cultural-Value Alignment
 - Individualism vs Collectivism (T)
 - Power-Distance Orientation (T)
 - Uncertainty-Avoidance (T)
 - ② Narrative-Resonance
 - Folklore / myth similarity (B)
 - ② Cultural-Openness
 - Cosmopolitanism (foreign-film receptivity) (T)
- ① IDEOLOGICAL SELECTIVITY (bias and identity filters ****inside**** culture)
 - ② Inclusivity / Diversity Attitude (T)
 - ② Ideological-Lean (Liberal ↔ Conservative) (T)
 - ② World-view Confirmation Bias (T)
- ① MORAL FOUNDATIONS (value emphasis that colours judgments)
 - ② Individualising
 - Care / Harm (T)
 - Fairness / Cheating (T)
 - ② Binding
 - Loyalty / Betrayal (T)
 - Authority / Subversion (T)
 - Sanctity / Degradation (T)
- ① COGNITIVE TRAIT ORIENTATION (how content is processed)
 - ② Complexity-Tolerance
 - Narrative-Complexity Preference (T)
 - Ambiguity Tolerance (T)
 - ② Processing-Mode
 - Intellectual Engagement (Need-for-Cognition) (T)
 - Sensation Seeking (Arousal-orientation) (T)
- ① EMOTIONAL MOTIVATION (why content is chosen)
 - ② Hedonic Pathway
 - Mood-Incongruent Escapism (T)
 - (driven in part by ↑ Sensation-Seeking)
 - ② Eudaimonic Pathway
 - Mood-Congruent Catharsis (T)
 - Self-Comparison Motive (Down | Up | None) (T)
 - Self-Identity Reinforcement (T)
 - (supported by ↑ Intellectual-Engagement)

Theoretical Model for Film x Audience Characterisation

How closely the film's cultural signals match the audience's values and heritage.

Theoretical Model for Film x Audience Characterisation

Theoretical Model for Film x Audience Characterisation

Theoretical Model for Film x Audience Characterisation

Does the film's narrative/
linguistic complexity sit at the
audience's sweet spot?

Theoretical Model for Film x Audience Characterisation

Whether the film satisfies the audience's dominant hedonic vs eudaimonic motive.

Our level of detail principle: Five big dials first – drill down only when we must.

Rule	Practice
R-1 Use only the five top dimensions (Cultural Context, Ideological Selectivity, Moral Foundations, Cognitive Trait, Emotional Motivation) for baseline comparisons.	Keeps the dashboard explainable.
R-2 Drop to the 2nd-level leaves only if a decision point needs it (e.g. two audiences tie on the Cultural dial, so we open Individualism vs Collectivism).	Prevents data overload.
R-3 Keep leaf scores internally numeric, but roll them up to a 5-point ordinal at the dimension level for presentation.	Supports your “five-value scale” concept.

Does the model support a 5-level valued dimensions and vars?

Reason	Elaboration	Explanation
1. Widely-used convention	<i>State-of-the-art precedent</i>	5-point ordinal scales dominate media-psychology metrics (e.g. Hofstede's cultural indices, MFT salience ratings, 5-point Likert in audience-bias studies), so adopting the same banding keeps our scores compatible with prior work.
2. From z-score to 5 levels	<i>Simple projection</i>	All raw micro-features from public surveys can be z-scaled ($\mu = 0, \sigma = 1$). We then slice the distribution into quintiles, e.g. $<-0.84 \text{ SD} = -2$, $-0.84 \text{--} -0.25 = -1$, $-0.25 \text{--} +0.25 = 0$, $+0.25 \text{--} +0.84 = +1$, $>+0.84 \text{ SD} = +2$. One line of code turns any continuous signal into the 5-band format.
3. LLM-driven saturation	<i>Binary/ternary \rightarrow 5-band</i>	Our LLM pipeline tags each review with binary/ternary micro-codes (e.g., Care+, Care-). A weighting function then sums and rescales those hits, drops them into the same quintile buckets, and outputs a full 5-level score per variable—and, by roll-up, per dimension.
4. Multi-source fusion	<i>Flexible data mix</i>	The same quintile logic ingests extra evidence—survey Likerts, z-scored national indices, or focus-group transcripts—via weighted averaging before the bucket step, giving one coherent 5-level value no matter how many sources inform it.

Data tiers and saturation method

Tier	Source	What we can score today	Role in MVP
T-0 Public stats	<i>Hofstede, WVS, Gallup, national box-office</i>	Cultural Context (IDV, PDI, UAI)	Baseline per country
T-1 Public text corpora	<i>Letterboxd, IMDb, RottenTomatoes, plot synopses</i>	All five dimensions via NLP/LLM pipelines	Model saturation (baseline)
T-2 Survey micros	<i>10-item online questionnaire (with or without Cineflux depending on possibility)</i>	Calibrates Ideological and emotional scores	Fine-tune target audiences
T-3 Cineflux data	<i>CineFlux</i>	Leaf-level nuance (e.g. Self-comparison motif)	Fine-tune target audiences

Update 7.3

9 June 2025

- Five-dimensional model stable. No further changes.
- Low-level saturation (binary/ternary) questions in final stages of design + validation.
- The problem of reliable saturation using LLMs has been solved.
- We considered input from Cathrin on film selection, need to formalise selection criteria.
- We asked to move digital FGs to September and end in mid October (check amendment).
- We are on track to have a wireframe mockup to demo beginning of September.
- Collected additional FG data on Amelia's children (Semente do Mal) for book chapter (*).
- Next: chapter on the topic-level foundation of the model, motivating next paper on 5D model.
- Next: saturated model from uncharacterised audience reviews PT + DK.
- Next: research seminar 30 June?

Personas dashboard key idea:

Establish a reference point, a source

See how a target audience moves in relation to that point.

For our MVP **source** will be **big, public data**, e.g. reviews and **target, digital FGs**

We produced a POC book chapter that precedes the 5D model, which was very welcome by editors.

Amelia's children

- 2023 Portuguese horror, English dialogue
- Provocative themes: occultism, incest, plastic-surgery grotesque
- Chosen because it mixes strong local identity with export-ready language

Source	N	Key traits
Letterboxd reviews	2 149	Multilingual, public, individual reactions
Digital focus groups	10 sessions, 80 undergraduates	WhatsApp-style chat; bot-moderated; balanced gender

ARTIFICAL FILMS produced by PRODUTORA GABRIEL ARRANTES • MARGARIDA LUCAS and BRUNO LINDY PAIVA • CARLOS COSTA ANABELA MOREIRA ALBA DAPPOIA
RUI BLANCO AMELIA'S CHILDREN written by GABRIEL ARRANTES and MARGARIDA LUCAS edited by PALLA STANE directed by GABRIEL ARRANTES
music by ANTONIO PINA art by JOAO VIEIRA production design by JOAO VIEIRA cast by JOAO VIEIRA and OLIVEIRA COSTA
production office: CA INSTITUTO DO CINEMA PORTUGUESO PERDIGAL FILM COMMISSION TUBERIA CINEMA PORTUGUESO • 1140 produced by GABRIEL ARRANTES MARGARIDA LUCAS and GABRIEL ARRANTES
CAA

1. Automatic GPT-4 translation → English
2. Prune to ≥ 5 -word, well-formed sentences
3. hSBM topic modelling → 19 bottom-level clusters (no preset k)
4. Manual coding → 8 abstract audience dimensions
5. Project FG utterances into the same semantic space and compute Δ emphasis

Review clusters

Word clusters

Cluster	Proportion	Title
1	25%	Chaotic and disturbingly entertaining bizarre horror.
2	10%	Saw the film because of actresses, got bizarre incest horror.
4	9%	Promising Portuguese atmosphere that only deliver inconsistency.
5	9%	From confusion to dark humour: this was very weird.
6	9%	Intriguing and atmospheric promise that deflated.
7	6%	Gabriel Abrantes' distinctive spin on Portuguese Horror.
9	7%	A weirdly unique Portuguese horror experience.
10	6%	Unintentionally hilarious and disturbingly surprising audience hit.
11	2%	DNA, and dark secrets: a narrative-driven portuguese horror.
13	2%	Extremely negative reviews: 'worst film ever'.
16	4%	Oddly enjoyable yet underdeveloped: missed potential.
17	2%	Cultural mix-up musical controversy: 'Garota de Ipanema'.
19	1%	Noteworthy weirdness: time is a whore that eats us like potatoes.

Table 2. Cluster Proportions and Descriptive Titles

Cluster	Proportion	Title
1	25%	Chaotic and disturbingly entertaining bizarre horror.
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Table 2. Cluster Proportions and Descriptive Titles

Topic clusters were mapped onto abstract categories via qualitative inductive coding

Dimension	Constituent clusters	$p_{\ell}^{(\text{reviews})}$
Cultural identity	7, 17	0.08
Moral values	2, 13	0.12
Humour	10	0.06
Narrative coherence and development	4, 11	0.11
Performance and characterization	1, 9, 16	0.36
Visual aesthetics and atmosphere	6	0.09
Dialogue and memorable quotes	19	0.01
Shock and extreme imagery	5	0.09
Other	Excluded clusters	0.08

Table 3. Clusters of Audience Reviews by Salient dimensions (Non-overlapping)

We projected the FG data (collected utterances per user) onto the same topic cluster space of the reviews, and mapped the result to the abstract dimensions. This allowed us to compute a displacement of the PT audience (target) from the source reference (Letterboxed reviews)

Figure 2. Paired dimension-shift, Δ_ℓ , plot comparing the proportional salience of each audience dimension, ℓ , in the Letterboxd review corpus (blue) with the corresponding salience in the focus-group corpus (red). Grey connectors emphasize the direction and magnitude of the shift for every dimension. All values sum to 100 per cent within each corpus, so any increase in one dimension must be offset by decreases elsewhere.

Some observations:

1. Expected differences in source and target became quantifiable in cultural identity (FGs spoke a lot more about that) and film performance (reviewers spoke a lot more about that)
2. An observation we could not explain yet is that most FGs did not focus on the moral aspects, especially the incest element. Some of them did mention that the mother PT symbolism had been taken to such extreme that it was destroyed.
3. FG target was not as horrified, by the visuals, they found it actually funny for the most part.
4. Big question: how can we go from here to insights funders care about?

Personas Dashboard MVP

Update November 2025

RECALL: Theoretical Model for Film x Audience Characterisation

- 1. Top level: dimensions
 - 2. Each dimension has features
 - 3. Each feature is saturated by a set of Boolean markers
 - 4. Saturation is done by LLM prompts
- This makes our inference engine accountable and explainable
No blackbox inferences.

- For each review, we have a vector:**
- Coarse (dimension) or
 - Granular (feature)
 - Scores are always [0,1]
 - And we have the review score (1 to 5)

What do we want from the dashboard?

Explain why some audience X likely reviewed a film selection Y in some way (positive, negative, and so on)

e.g. PT audience rated DK 2024 dramas low citing mainly MORAL arguments

Note. we have streamlined and reduced this model.

The challenges to this innovation

- **Accurate detection of audience signals:** Even with sophisticated AI systems, signals such as empathy, as expressed in public reviews, can be hard to detect. The tradeoff between lightweight prompting and performance matters. **The FG approach to segmented audiences** targets audience signals directly
- **Inherent variability:** People rate the same films in very different ways. We focus on the detection of **review score biases** (positive, neutral or negative) as well as, when bias is neutral, the possibility of **polarisation**.
- **Connecting these values to potential explanations** derived from our model when evidence from review data supports explanatory hypotheses. Here, we rely on AI and Data Science to quantify the strength of association between features on our model and rating patterns

RECALL: For each review, we have a vector:

- Coarse (dimension) or
- Granular (feature)
- Scores are always [0,1]
- And we have the review score (1 to 5)

What do we want?

Explain why some audience X reviewed a film selection Y in some way,

Core explanatory quantitative metrics in the dashboard:

- **Dimensional signal score**, e.g. *how much* morality? (quantitative)
- **Net review score polarity** (direction of *bias*, pos/neg/neu quantitative)
- **Polarisation index** (degree of review score *disagreement*, quantitative)

Dashboard includes natural language rolling insights

The MVP basics

A. **Entry point:** user makes a film SELECTION based on:

- Producer countries
- Genres
- Release year range
- If for the SELECTION there is specific SEGMENTED audience data the user can select SEGMENT.

B. **Loading.** The SYSTEM picks the films in the selection and computes the similarity matrix based on how each of them scored in our audience model.

C. **Preprocessing.** If the SYSTEM identifies separated CLUSTERS of films based on their audience profiles, the dashboard will adapt to allow the user to focus on the SELECTION as a whole, or on each of the existing CLUSTERS.

D. **Display Dashboard.** The SYSTEM has a set of informative WIDGETS.

Demo mockup

Core epistemic stance: not predictive, but explanatory

Given people's words and ratings, what can we learn about how and why they evaluate films as they do?

This shift has some important implications:

- Ontological (from behaviour to **cognition + culture**)
- Output (from forecasts to **explanations**)
- Use case (from control to **understanding**).

The dashboard is thus **not a recommender, not a sentiment monitor, and not a forecaster** but a cognitive map of audience reasoning.

What “explanatory” means in data-science and AI terms

- A. Model interpretability first.** We use transparent aggregation (markers → variables → dimensions). Each value is semantically meaningful, not a hidden weight.
- B. Causal and relational emphasis.** We explore relationships like “low ratings likely due to high moral signal” (for some audiences) without claiming to predict future ratings. Structural explanation, not forecasting.
- C. Error not as failure, but as ambiguity.** Polarisation and variance are not noise; they are phenomena, i.e., the externalisation of disagreement and complexity in audience reasoning.

Why our explanatory stance is innovative?

- A. It is epistemically clear.** Most competitors are epistemically confused: they make blind predictions without understanding.
- B. It has true value for the EU.** Cultural agencies and film funds don't actually need to predict the next hit. They need to explain why audiences respond differently across cultures, regions, and narratives.
- C. Transparency and legitimacy.** Because each metric is grounded in interpretable dimensions, variables and markers (our hierarchical model), stakeholders can audit and discuss the reasoning, not just consume a mysterious "AI score".

Next steps

- A. Finalising the model saturation system by **14 NOV**
- B. Reducing the model as necessary to ensure MVP success by **14 NOV**
- C. Saturate for demo data (PT and DK films) in the set intersected with Cathrine's DB (by **20 Nov**)
- D. Fine-tuning UX (by **1 Dec**)
- E. Report writing is ongoing, finalised by **1 Dec**